

Graphical Abstract

The macroeconomic impact of policy measures, technological progress and societal attitude in energy transition scenarios

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Highlights

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- We address the macroeconomic effects of five climate scenarios using two CGE models.
- We focus on the effects of changes in society, technology, and policy.
- We incorporate climate change effects through labor productivity.
- Effect of decarbonization on GDP is moderate under given technological improvement.
- Decarbonization scenarios result in relatively large sectoral shifts.

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Abstract

This paper compares the macroeconomic impacts of different decarbonization storylines until 2050 using two Computable General Equilibrium models. The modeling shocks are harmonized across models to simulate four decarbonization scenarios through three main drivers: technical development, societal attitude, and policies. The study explores the contribution of each of these drivers to the European decarbonization. The results show that the decarbonization scenarios have moderate effects on GDP; decarbonization scenarios rather result in sectoral shifts. The impact of temperature on labor productivity minimally alters expected growth levels, since larger differences in temperature between the scenarios are only expected to occur in 2100, not yet in 2050. Electricity demand is increasing in all scenarios, particularly with stronger political guidance leading to additional tax and subsidy measures to encourage the use of electricity and discourage fossil-based fuels. When society is a driving factor, it is found that circular business models result in an increase in the service industry but might have a slightly negative impact on overall growth due to stronger spillover effects linked to the manufacturing industry. Technology appears to be the only driver to facilitate decarbonization while maintaining steady economic growth.

Keywords: Computable General Equilibrium Models, Energy Transition, Scenario analysis

1. Introduction

The effects of global warming are already visible on the planet. Temperatures are increasing all around the world, ice is melting in polar ice caps and mountain glaciers, lakes are warming up, animals are changing migration patterns, plants' seasonal activities are changing, and some areas observe colder-than-normal winters and more heatwaves with a risk factor for an increase in wildfires [1]. Generally, it is accepted that the main cause of the current global warming is the excess greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions related to human activities, in particular from burning fossil fuels [2].

The mitigation of the increasingly visible events and consequences of global warming is one of the biggest challenges of humankind. At the same time, national governments feel the need to keep the economy competitive, thriving, and fair for its population. Global warming - as the word suggests - is a global problem, and cannot single-handedly be solved by individual countries. One typical example is carbon leakage. When implemented by only one country, industries have a strong incentive to relocate their activities to more profitable production environments where climate policies are less stringent. This is not only undesirable for the country - risking losing employment and economic value - but also globally, as emissions are

not reduced. Thus, a global effort in reducing future GHG emissions is necessary. The Paris Agreement, following the 2015 Climate Change Conference, was a big step towards a low-carbon future. Countries have to submit their national independent contribution (INDC), expressing in which way they aim at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and reducing the risk and impact of climate change [3].

Still, the dialogue between policymakers, researchers, and industry can be further improved. This paper aims at contributing to this challenge by giving insight into the different ways to get to a low carbon-emissions system. It builds upon the four qualitative storylines developed in the H2020 project openENTRANCE ([4], [5]). This paper makes use of both the quantified scenarios of an energy system model and the underlying qualitative storylines. In this work, we provide a uni-directional soft link between the energy system model GENeSYS-MOD and two Computable General Equilibrium models to give insight about the socioeconomic and environmental effects of the four alternative decarbonization storylines. Quantification of the impact on the energy system has been done by [4] with the help of GENeSYS-MOD, a cost-optimizing linear program focusing on long-term pathways for the different sectors of the energy system.

The drivers used for the development of the storylines

are based on three key uncertainties. That is, it is highly uncertain how fast technologies will develop (1. technology novelty), how seriously society will undertake the transition towards a low-carbon future (2. smart society), and whether the European governments will adopt policies to facilitate the transition (3. policy exertion). Three ambitious storylines – aiming at a maximum of 1.5 degree temperature increase with respect to 1990 levels – each place an emphasis on two of the drivers: Directed transition combines technology novelty and policy exertion, Techno-Friendly combines technology novelty and smart society and Societal Commitment combines smart society and policy exertion as drivers. The fourth storyline, called Gradual Development, aims to limit the temperature increase to a maximum of 2 degrees. It incorporates elements from all key drivers towards decarbonization but with lesser intensity. To provide a useful benchmark for the analyses of the aforementioned storylines a fifth storyline has been modeled representing a Business-as-Usual situation.

In this paper, we present a comparative analysis of the expected environmental and socioeconomic impacts of the decarbonization storylines until the year 2050 using two Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models: REMES-EU and EXIOMOD. CGE models are commonly used for assessing the socioeconomic impacts of future scenarios. Alternatives for these types of assessments are econometric and partial equilibrium models, input-output (I-O) models, or integrated assessment models (IAM). CGE models are closely related to Input-Output models. I-O models, though, only consider volume effects, while price effects are neglected as well as utility optimizing behavior of the different agents in the model. While these elements are also incorporated in most econometric and partial equilibrium models, these latter types are not capable of detecting the interplay among the involved variables. Partial equilibrium models generally only analyze specific industries in more detail. This can be very useful when the focus of the study is on only a selection of sectors. However, for this study we are also interested in the interactions between the sectors, the effects on prices, and the economy as a whole, which makes CGE models a more suitable choice. IAM combine information from different systems, like economic, earth, and climate systems, and their interaction, even though the impact of climate change is not always fed back into the macroeconomic models to define how it might impact the productivity of the different production sectors. Here, we utilize the concepts introduced by Nobel Prize Laureate William Nordhaus ([6]) by including climate feedback effects in both CGE models. Namely, we model lower labor productivity in proportion to the expected rise in temperature in the different European countries as a consequence of the produced emissions.

The model comparison provides insights into the level of confidence in the results and the extent to which they are sensitive to the choice of model. Also, while most analyses only consider the effects of policy measures, behavioral

changes, and targets on the economy and environment, in this paper we also consider the negative effects of climate change on labor productivity.

Several analyses have been done to understand the impact of decarbonization on the economy. Our analysis shows that the decarbonization scenarios have only moderate effects on GDP, they rather result in large sectoral shifts. These results seem consistent with what is found in the literature. [7] computes the economic impact of a shift towards a renewable electricity mix in the Netherlands using CGE model ThreeME. They find that the expected increase in GDP is only 1%. [8] explores the economic impacts of a low-carbon economy by 2030 using the econometric model E3ME, they find a small positive impact of 1.1% on the economic activity, where the variation between sectors is considerable. In addition, they find a positive effect on employment due to all investments that are required to achieve the transition.

In this article, we soft-link an energy-system model to two macroeconomic models to ensure realistic energy requirements for the sectors in the economy. The soft-linking approach is often used in the literature, for example by [7], [9], and [10]. The latter can be closely used as a benchmark for our approach. It discusses the potential economic impacts of a global climate action scenario in which global greenhouse gas emissions fall by 72% by 2050, in relation to a reference scenario. The decarbonization scenario is characterized by a negative impact on GDP, primarily due to reductions in private consumption as a result of changes in competitiveness in the exports of goods and services. Other results show that RES deployment in power generation is notable, with a significant use of biofuels in the transport sector. The transition to a low-carbon system is capital-intensive and leads to a slight increase in energy costs and a crowding-out effect in the economy. However, the avoided climate damages and co-benefits for air pollution, noise, and other externalities largely over-compensate the small direct economic costs. The macroeconomic impacts of the EU28 decarbonization strategy strongly depend on the level of mitigation action of major trading partners. Early action and adoption of measures for the preparation towards the low-carbon transition can give a comparative advantage to the European energy-intensive and low-carbon technology sectors. The results obtained by this study are largely in line with our findings, especially the ones about the large deployment of electricity as a source of energy and the need to achieve technological improvements as early as possible, which are the only economically efficient way to accommodate for the requirements set by policy.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the CGE models used for the analysis and the most important differences across the two models. Section 3 gives more insight into the scenarios. The most important results are presented in Section 4 and 5, where Section 4 shows the effect of individual scenarios on economy and environment and Section 5 analyses the effects of

the three main underlying drivers that define the scenarios (political, societal and technological). A critical view of the results along with a conclusion and suggestions for further research are given in Section 6.

2. Macroeconomic models

We carry out our analyses using two Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models: EXIOMOD, hosted at the department of Strategic Business Analysis at TNO in the Netherlands, and REMES-EU hosted at the Department of Industrial Economics and Technology Management, NTNU in Norway. The two models are part of a larger energy transition modeling suite developed within the EU funded openENTRANCE project.

EXIOMOD’s name stands for EXtended Input-Output MODEL. “Extended” refers to the fact that EXIOMOD can take both the form of a standard Input-Output (IO) analysis or a CGE model and allows the modeler to change the regional and sectorial segmentation as well as the level of complexity regarding the specification of the model by switching on or off specific blocks.

REMES-EU stands for Regional Equilibrium Model with focus on the Energy System and represents a multi-regional, multi-sectoral CGE model. It has been designed primarily to analyze the impacts of different climate policy measures and the interactions between the economies of the European Countries.

Figure 1 illustrates a general structure of a CGE model. The economy is in balance when total market demand equals total market supply for each agent and output market. Total demand comes from households, governments, investments, and other industries’ consumption as well as from exports. The demand is covered by internal production and by imports. Production requires capital, labor, energy, and materials. Wages, profits, and intermediate costs are the remuneration for the factor inputs, with capital and labor providing the income for final demand agents to pay for consumption. The model starts from an equilibrium between supply and demand, and a shock, such as a tax increase or improved factor productivity, brings the economy out of balance. Behavioral and accounting equations ensure a new equilibrium, through a price adaptation mechanism. Many CGE models also include environmental extensions to analyze both the economic and the environmental effects of policies.

The models differ in their modeling structures, with EXIOBASE being modeled as a nonlinear system ([11]), while REMES-EU is modeled as a Mixed Complementarity Problem ([12, 13, 14]), on the depth of data used, and the way they model CO₂ caps and related prices. Although both models use EXIOBASE ([15]) as a dataset, their base years, sectors, commodities, and the number of modeled countries differ (see Table 2). Both models have the option to aggregate regions, products, and industries. EXIOMOD uses a KLEM structure to model the production sectors, while REMES-EU uses a KLEM-R structure to

Figure 1: General structure of a CGE model.

	EXIOMOD	REMES-EU
Base year	2011	2007
Number of regions	49 (44 countries among which the 27 EU regions, and 5 aggregated RoW regions)	29 (EU27 without Croatia but with the inclusion of Norway, Switzerland and Great Britain)
Number of products	200	32
Number of industries	163	24

Table 1: Main characteristics of Supply and Use tables underlying to EXIOMOD and REMES-EU

model resource-dependent sectors such as refineries, with elasticities taken from [16]. The models also differ in their modeling of regions representing the rest of the world. Additionally, the implementation of some decarbonization scenarios requires a gradual uptake of hydrogen-based solutions, which is included in a slightly different manner in each model, but whose production structure is based in both models on [17], also including CCS activities ([18]). The analysis aims to identify the extent to which the two models with different approaches to model emissions control yield similar results. For more details on the differences between the two models, the reader may refer to Appendices I and II.

3. The openENTRANCE scenarios

An important component of the openENTRANCE project is the definition of consistent storylines compatible with the Paris Climate Agreement (Deliverable 7.1 of openENTRANCE project ([5])). Many storylines and scenarios have been developed in the past (for example SSP and RCP scenarios from IPCC [19], Energy Roadmap 2050 scenarios [20], EUCO scenarios, ‘a clean planet for all’ scenarios [21]). The openENTRANCE storyline descriptions are based on a thorough analysis of these already existing global and European pathways and scenario studies. A review of existing storylines, scenarios, and pathways

shows that we are confronted with different kinds of uncertainties when trying to describe the future energy system. Three key uncertainties were chosen as main drivers of the openENTRANCE storylines: a) Society's attitude and lifestyle. How flexible will the individual and collective society be, and how seriously will responsibility for transitioning towards a low-carbon energy world be undertaken? Under a 'smart society', engagement and awareness of society to implement concrete actions are central. b) Novelty and availability of technologies. Technological progress has always been a big uncertainty. Will technological progress develop fast enough to support a smooth transition towards a low-carbon energy world? Under 'technological novelty', innovation and technological breakthroughs help to foster the energy transition. c) Geopolitical and economic development. Will there be a smooth global energy transition towards a low-carbon society accompanied by harmonic geopolitical developments that support the transition? Or will it be a disruptive global energy transition with geopolitical tensions and uneven distribution of economic prosperity? Under 'policy exertion', the world is steered towards a low-carbon energy world via the implementation of detailed policy measures.

In openENTRANCE, four storylines have been developed. Each storyline is defined by a combination of two key drivers/uncertainties (see Figure 2). The storylines are as follows:

- Directed transition (DT), characterized by technological novelty and policy exertion.
- Techno-Friendly (TF), characterized by technological novelty and smart society.
- Societal commitment (SC), characterized by smart society and policy exertion.
- Gradual development (GD), considering all of the previous drivers but in a smaller extent.

In the remainder of the document, we will regularly refer to the storylines via their abbreviations DT, TF, SC, and GD. Storylines DT, TF, and SC aim at reaching a limit of 1.5°C temperature increase by 2100, while GD is more moderate with an aim of at most 2°C temperature increase.

3.1. Quantified input to the model

While storylines are by definition qualitative, macroeconomic models require quantitative inputs, which are obtained by translating these storylines into numbers. Part of the quantified input is coming from the linking with an energy system model, GENeSYS-MOD. The soft-linking has been performed as shown in Figure 3, with GENeSYS-MOD kickstarting the two macroeconomic models providing the development of the energy mix in the different sectors according to the storylines as shown by the black connection. The CGE models also define common assumptions to model the scenarios directly out of the storylines as shown by the light grey connections.

Figure 2: Pathways storylines typology = policy exertion x technological novelty x smart society. The three dimensions set the scene on three disruptors or uncertainties which together creates four storylines (colored squares).

Figure 3: Soft linking process between GENeSYS-MOD and the EXIOMOD and REMES-EU CGE models.

Additional modeling assumptions - specifically for macroeconomic models - have been defined for each scenario. Table 2 summarizes the translation of storyline features into quantitative inputs for the models. Compared to the initial openENTRANCE scenarios we consider an additional storyline feature: climate feedback effects, reflecting the lower labor productivity due to higher expected temperatures.

The macroeconomic effects of the openENTRANCE scenarios are compared to a reference scenario. The motivation behind the development of the reference scenario is twofold: first and foremost it is used as a realistic Business-as-Usual scenario to which the other scenarios can be compared in 2050. The reference scenario is assumed to have a much milder decarbonization path toward 2050. Moreover, the reference scenario is used to calibrate some of the parameters such as the long-term labor productivity trend in the EU that remain the same across scenarios² while ensuring that the GDP growth reflects the one featured in the EU Reference Scenario [22].

4. Comparative macroeconomic analysis of the openENTRANCE pathways

This section presents the results of the four openENTRANCE scenarios and compares them with the Reference scenario across the two models. Most figures and tables present the model outcomes in indices with respect to 2020 or percentage change in 2050 with respect to the reference scenario. This makes it easier to compare the results across the two models than using the original units. While both models use EXIOBASE as the underlying dataset, the version and base year of the data are different. On top of that, small modifications or additions to the databases have been made for the calibration of the two different CGE models (see Appendix I). Secondly, when comparing the growth or decline of different sectors in one figure, an index makes the comparison easier.

4.1. Economic impact

4.1.1. Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Figure 4 gives the trend in Gross Domestic Product for the EU for all scenarios³. The measures that have most effect on GDP over the years are (1) the improvements in capital and labor productivity (increasing effect) (2) the improved energy efficiency (increasing effect), (3) the

²We model the productivity of labor reduction due to climate change as a multiplicative shock to the baseline productivity, which remains the same across scenarios.

³Note that - despite that both models calibrated labor productivity in the Reference scenario to exactly the same growth rates of GDP - still the index of GDP in 2050 for the Reference scenario is slightly different when compared for the two models. The explanation is the different underlying databases with deviating country weights in aggregated GDP for the EU.

Figure 4: Index of Gross Domestic Product for four openENTRANCE scenarios and the reference scenario between 2020 and 2050. Results for EXIOMOD are given in the top panel, while results for REMES-EU are in the bottom panel. This figure includes climate change feedback on the economy. When these effects are neglected, GDP in 2050 in the reference is 1.3% higher, 0.8% for GD, 0.5% for SC, and 0.6% for DT and TF. For REMES-EU, these changes are respectively 0.6%, 0.4%, 0.3%, 0.3%, and 0.3%.

cap on carbon emissions (decreasing effect) and (4) the negative impact of climate change on labor productivity (decreasing effect). When comparing the four openENTRANCE scenarios to the reference scenario, it is found that scenarios GD and SC display a similar GDP development as the reference scenario. The deviations compared to the reference scenario are also quite similar across the two models. GDP is between 1,1-1,5% lower than the reference scenario in 2050. These two scenarios have the same energy efficiency assumption as the Reference scenario. Scenarios with higher energy efficiency have resulted in slightly different GDP levels across models. In particular, REMES-EU is very sensitive to the stronger energy efficiency assumptions in the Techno-Friendly scenario. (see Figure 2).

4.1.2. Sectoral output

Sectoral output is defined as the value of output sold to other agents (total revenue), which is by definition equal to the sum of spending on intermediate use, capital costs,

Storyline feature	Sources and motivation of quantification	Implementation in the models
Performance of Global Economy/ Markets	GDP of EU regions follow for the reference scenario the growth projections of the EU-reference scenario ([22]). GDP of developing regions outside the EU follows growth from the OECD scenario ([23]) when this storyline feature gives 'uneven distribution of economic wealth'. When this storyline feature gives 'global prosperity', these regions grow slightly faster to catch up with developed regions. Population growth in EU has been taken from the EU reference scenario and from OECD for regions outside the EU. Population projections are the same for all scenarios.	GDP growth is implemented via sectoral productivity. Growth in population is implemented via exogenous growth in the labor force. GDP growth of regions outside the EU is endogenously modeled in EXIOMOD. REMES-EU adjusts the exogenous trade relation with rest-of-the-world regions.
Global/ International Climate Policies	CO ₂ cap is assumed to decrease by 40% in the reference scenario, by 70-80% in scenario GD, by 80-90% under SC and DT, and by 90-100% under the scenario TF. Reductions are with respect to the base year 1990 and are implemented for European regions only. The reductions are taken from the element 'GHG emission reduction' in Tables 4.2(a)-4.2(d) in Deliverable 7.1 ([5]).	The GHG restrictions are included by introducing an additional carbon cap module to the model. See Appendix II for more detail and the differences in implementation across the two models.
Resource Exploitation, Circular Economy: Level of Importance, Contribution to Circular Economy	A shift from the use of materials to the use of services. Depending on the scenario, either all countries join in the servitization process or only a selection of countries. Under GD, most countries reduce their preference for materials by 20%, moving this preference towards services. Under SC this amount goes to 35% and to 5% for TF. There is no servitization assumption in the Reference scenario.	For servitization, the exogenous demand share of industrial and aluminum products is reduced for each sector that uses these products. The demand share of services is increased with the corresponding aggregated decrease of the two product groups. This ensures that the total intermediate costs of a sector remain the same.
GHG emission reduction targets	The models implemented a carbon cap (also see Global/ International Climate policies). In addition, the models have implemented for all scenarios a reduction trajectory of carbon efficiencies . This represents the reduction in emissions due to decarbonization efforts in industries. The carbon efficiency quantification assumption has been taken from the EU reference scenario [22].	Carbon efficiencies are implemented via exogenous CO ₂ -coefficients.
Preferable Climate and Energy policies	Under DT and SC, climate goals are reached due to stricter policies. For these scenarios, there is a subsidy on the use of electricity (5%) and an additional tax on the use of unsustainable fuels (5%) for both households and industries.	Tax and subsidy rates are exogenous factors that raise or lower the consumer price of a product. These rates are adjusted for scenarios DT and SC.
Incentives for R&D / pilots	R&D efforts make industries more energy efficient . The energy efficiency projection for our reference, GD, and SC has been taken from the EU reference scenario [22]. Storyline DT and TF assume higher levels of technological novelty (see Figure 2), and higher energy efficiency is assumed for these scenarios.	Energy efficiency is implemented via a higher productivity of energy, i.e. with the same amount of energy, more economic output is realized. Higher productivity of energy is implemented via an increase of scalar 'energy productivity' in the KLE CES-production function.
The energy and transport sectors: Role of Existing/ Known/ Novel Technologies: candidates (Production Complementary)	The shares of energy types used for the transport sector is taken from GENeSYS-MOD scenario. The reference scenario does not include this assumption. Also, the technology mix for the production of electricity is taken from GENeSYS-MOD scenario. The technology mix assumption from GD is also applied to the reference scenario. The relative share of hydrogen with respect to aggregate hydrogen plus natural gas is also taken from GENeSYS-MOD.	REMES-EU and EXIOMOD include the external data from GENeSYS-MOD in different ways. Namely, REMES-EU has one power sector, whereas EXIOMOD differentiates between 10 different types of electricity, defined by the technology that produces the electricity. In REMES-EU the consumption of energy commodities (energy input) by the (single) power sector is changed over time according to the values provided by Genesys-Mod as input. In EXIOMOD the GENeSYS-MOD external data trigger a reallocation of weight of the different power technologies in terms of total electricity output.
Energy sectors: resources	In the reference scenario, the factor that influences the oil extraction decreases by 10% every five years. For the other scenarios, this is 15% every five years.	A shift in the use of energy products by the transport sector is implemented via the (exogenously given) intermediate consumption coefficients. For each European region, the transport sector changes the shares of the different energy products used in its production. Note that the total intermediate input shares for the transport sectors should still add up to the aggregate in the base case. This scenario does not imply efficiency in production costs.
Energy sectors: structure and demand of subsector Industry	Industries switch to different energy input types. This data is taken from the GENeSYS-MOD for scenarios GD, TF, DT, and SC. The reference scenario does not assume an external input for the shift in the use of energy.	This scenario element is only implemented in REMES-EU, via an oil extraction factor.
Energy sectors: structure and demand of the tertiary and commercial sector	Households and services switch to different energy input types. This data is taken from the GENeSYS-MOD for scenarios GD, TF, DT, and SC. The reference scenario does not assume a shift in the use of energy.	This is implemented via the (exogenously given) intermediate consumption coefficients of the service industry. (Similar to how GENeSYS-MOD energy shares are implemented for the transport sector). In addition, in EXIOMOD this input from GENeSYS-MOD is also used to adjust the (exogenously given) household energy consumption shares.
Added storyline feature: climate feedback effects	Higher temperatures are assumed to decrease labor productivity ([24]). For each country in the EU and each scenario, the expected effect on labor productivity has been calculated and implemented in the models. For this, Figure 7.1 of [25] has been used for expected temperature increases under a Business-as-Usual situation. Average temperatures in Europe are taken from [26], and the distribution of temperature increases over countries has been taken from Figure 1 of [27].	Both models implement the climate feedback effects via a decrease in labor productivity

Table 2: Translation of storyline features into quantitative input to the macroeconomic models. Details described in 'Sources and motivation of quantification' can be found in [5].

labor costs, profits, and taxes minus subsidies (total costs). By looking at the size of sectoral output, one can detect which sectors are dominant in the European economy.

The two models produce fairly similar results in terms of effects on sectoral output. In the *reference scenario*, growth in fossil-based energy sectors is expected to be limited or already slightly decreasing with respect to 2020. Other non-energy sectors, like manufacturing, service, aluminum, and transport are expected to follow a growth of 40-60% between 2020 and 2050. These sectors are least affected by the energy efficiency assumption or the modest cap on carbon emissions. In fact, they are mostly benefiting from the improved capital and labor productivity, since they follow the same growth as GDP. In EXIOMOD, the electricity sector is increasing quite rapidly already in the reference scenario because it includes the energy mix from the energy system model already in the reference scenario, while REMES-EU does not. Under a (moderate) carbon cap it is optimal for the market to demand more electricity when electricity is, over the years, produced using a cleaner mix.

Comparing the effects of these more ambitious targets (GD, TF, DT, SC) on the growth of European sectors (see Table 3), it is found that almost all sectors are expected to face a lower growth (or further decline) compared to the reference situation in 2050. This is mainly caused by the tightening carbon cap. There are two exceptions, i.e. the sector(s) that produce(s) electricity and the service sector.

Electricity becomes a cleaner substitute for fossil-based fuel types, this shift is necessary to stay under the tightening cap on carbon. The demand for electricity is discussed in more detail in Section 4.1.3.

The service sector is also growing in size due to the servitization assumption. That is, it is assumed that households gradually shift from owning to leasing goods. Especially in the scenario SC society is particularly motivated to move towards circular business models, which is shown by a remarkably high increase in the activity level of the service sector, and a relatively large decrease in the manufacturing and aluminum sectors with respect to the reference in 2050.

The uptake of hydrogen is assumed not to be part of the reference scenario, which makes it impossible to compute a growth rate with respect to the reference situation. It is therefore left out of Table 3. Instead, the ratio of hydrogen with respect to hydrogen plus natural gas aggregate is given in the caption. EXIOMOD takes the shares from GENeSYS-MOD to gradually shift the demand for gas from being produced by the natural gas sector towards the new hydrogen sector. Until 2040-2045 the hydrogen sector is increasing; afterward, the strict cap on carbon also results in a decrease in demand for gas and an increase in demand for electricity. Thus, also sectoral output in the hydrogen sector is declining. This effect is seen in all decarbonization scenarios. In REMES-EU after 2035, electricity is rather substituted by hydrogen, which explains the slightly higher shares of hydrogen with respect to hy-

drogen plus natural gas aggregate.

4.1.3. Electricity demand

Demand for electricity is expected to increase fast under the openENTRANCE scenarios. This result is shown by both models. Exogenous technology development on the use of energy products in manufacturing, service, transport sectors, and households force these sectors to shift away from fossil-based energy types and use electricity instead. Moreover, demand shifts towards cleaner energy sources under a tightening carbon cap. The shift from producing hydrogen instead of natural gas also causes an increase in electricity production, because the hydrogen sector has a high electricity use. Scenarios DT and SC show the highest increase in electricity demand. These scenarios strongly promote the use of clean energy products over fossil-based energy products via additional taxes and subsidies. EXIOMOD shows an even faster increase in electricity when compared to REMES-EU. This difference can be explained via the assumptions on how the scenario is modeled in the two models - like the additional electricity technology-mix assumption that is only implemented in EXIOMOD - but also the differences in dynamics and equations that form the model. For example, in REMES-EU, blue hydrogen is a good substitute for electricity. In the results from REMES-EU openENTRANCE scenarios show a decline in electricity after 2035, which is when the substitution of electricity by hydrogen kicks in.

The increase in electricity is compensated by a steep decrease in demand for fossil-based energy types, which is fairly similar for the two models.

4.1.4. Commodity prices

In macroeconomic models, prices act as mediating drivers to obtain an equilibrium between supply and demand. An exogenous increase in demand for a product is balanced by an increase in price, which mitigates the initial demand increase and compensates it with an equal increase in supply. As explained in Appendix I, the two models have some differences in the way they have been designed. We emphasize this by showing the response of the models' energy prices for Germany. EXIOMOD shows that energy prices are in 2050 higher under the ambitious climate scenarios (GD, SC, DT, TF) compared to prices in the reference scenario, while REMES-EU shows the opposite (see Table 4). The reason for these differences is the following: in EXIOMOD, CO₂ price acts as a production tax and directly increases the purchase price of fossil-based energy products. Energy products responsible for high emissions levels will experience a large increase in production costs. Depending on the tightness of the carbon cap, this effect can be stronger or weaker. In REMES-EU, the CO₂ allowances are supposed to be purchased alongside fossil fuels in proportion to the amount of emission that a particular fuel produces in a given sector. The increase in CO₂ price due to the lower carbon cap over time, leads to

Sector	EXIOMOD				REMES-EU			
	GD	SC	DT	TF	GD	SC	DT	TF
Agriculture	-4%	-10%	-5%	-3%	-6%	-17%	-11%	-6%
Coal extraction	-54%	-62%	-62%	-62%	-32%	-48%	-46%	-58%
Crude oil and natural gas extraction	-44%	-77%	-76%	-76%	-62%	-74%	-73%	-81%
Manufacturing industry	-4%	-12%	-7%	-2%	-7%	-17%	-12%	-2%
Aluminium production	-12%	-33%	-21%	-5%	-11%	-32%	-21%	-12%
Trade and distribution of electricity and gas	-3%	-8%	-3%	-2%	0%	-1%	1%	0%
Natural gas	-72%	-86%	-85%	-80%	-31%	-59%	-57%	-73%
Services	3%	10%	7%	3%	3%	10%	6%	2%
Transport Services	-5%	-15%	-11%	-7%	-6%	-7%	-5%	3%
Electricity production	58%	67%	59%	46%	68%	84%	102%	81%

Table 3: Percentage change of total output for four openENTRANCE scenarios with respect to the Reference scenario in 2050 for EU27 and ten sectors. The ratio of hydrogen with respect to hydrogen plus natural gas aggregate is for scenario GD, SC, DT, and TF respectively 55%, 57%, 50% and 40% for EXIOMOD. For REMES-EU these shares are respectively equal to 66%, 64%, 57%, 61%.

a decrease in demand for fossil fuels which, in turn, leads to a decrease in the purchase price of the aforementioned fuels.

4.2. Environmental impact

CO₂ emissions are decreasing over the years. In the final years before 2050, the CO₂ emissions are exactly equal to the CO₂ cap. A positive CO₂ price is needed to keep emissions within the strict cap. In earlier years right after 2020, it was possible that other measures (like energy efficiency, technology change, taxes, and subsidies or exogenous energy demand shares from GENesYS-MOD) resulted in enough reduction in emissions that not all EU countries needed to set a price on emissions.

When the carbon cap becomes strict, countries need a higher CO₂ price as a driver to keep emissions within the CO₂ cap. Both models show that as of 2045, the price of CO₂ starts to increase exponentially. The last 20% of CO₂ emissions is more costly than the previous 80%.

5. Simulation of the impacts of the three main drivers on the economy and decarbonization

The openENTRANCE storylines are determined according to the changes of three main drivers: society, technology, and policy (see Figure 2). One of the main objectives of the economic analyses performed under this project is to simulate how much each of these drivers has an impact on key macroeconomic indicators: i.e. effects on GDP, demand for electricity and fossil-based fuels, the size of the service sector and the price of CO₂. Table 5 illustrates the effects of the drivers as a percentage change relative to the situation where this driver would not be taken into account.

Societal Driver. Under the driver "smart society", society is intrinsically motivated to move toward a clean and sustainable future. This is modeled via the servitization assumption in which there is a gradual shift from purchasing manufactured goods to the purchase of services (i.e. repair and leasing services to ensure a longer lifespan). In general, the production of services is obtained with a lower amount of intermediate (manufactured and

Figure 5: Index of electricity demand on EU level for the Reference scenario between 2020 and 2050. Results for EXIOMOD are given in the top panel, and results for REMES-EU are in the bottom panel.

Commodity	EXIOMOD				REMES-EU			
	GD	SC	DT	TF	GD	SC	DT	TF
Crude Oil	35%	197%	196%	210%	-5%	-5%	8%	3%
Gasoline	36%	198%	197%	209%	-62%	-62%	-61%	-66%
Diesel	35%	196%	195%	207%	-31%	-32%	-32%	-41%
Heavy distillate	34%	189%	188%	200%	-41%	-42%	-38%	-46%
Natural gas	31%	64%	78%	90%	-6%	-7%	0%	-7%
Coal	54%	156%	154%	171%	-30%	-35%	-32%	-43%
Biofuels	-2%	-10%	-11%	-10%	-60%	-61%	-50%	-48%
Other fuels	35%	193%	191%	204%	-60%	-68%	-65%	-72%
Electricity	8%	23%	21%	36%	11%	7%	11%	16%

Table 4: Percentage change of energy commodity prices for four openENTRANCE scenarios with respect to the Reference scenario in 2050 for Germany

Figure 6: Total CO₂ emissions for the Reference scenario and four openENTRANCE scenarios between 2008 and 2050. Data between 2008-2020 is based on historic trajectories from Eurostat. Results for EXIOMOD are given in the top panel, and results for REMES-EU are in the bottom panel.

Figure 7: CO₂ price for the Reference scenario and four openENTRANCE scenarios between 2008 and 2050. Results for EXIOMOD are given in the top panel, and results for REMES-EU are in the bottom panel.

energy) products. So an increase in demand for services is expected to entail the formation of a smaller multiplier for the economy. Manufacturing a product from raw materials requires more energy than repairing an existing product or sharing a product among multiple consumers, this explains the lower energy use under the societal driver. Even though the lower demand for manufactured goods is offset by higher demand for services, these latter produce smaller ripple effects through the other sectors of the economy. As a result, GDP might be lower compared to the scenario where the circular economy paradigm is not adopted. A shift to an intrinsically motivated service-intensive economy with lower energy requirements also implies that decarbonization should not be enforced via a higher CO₂ price alone.

Technological Driver. The change in technology has been modeled using different shocks. The first shock is a change in the energy mix featured in the different sectors based on the information provided by technology-detailed energy system models and the second shock is an improvement in energy efficiency over time. The inclusion of external development of the energy mix is considered under every openENTRANCE scenario via the soft-link with the GENeSYS-MOD energy system model, while the improvement of the energy efficiency (over the baseline efficiency development) has been only considered under the Techno-Friendly scenario. For this reason, we only restrict to this aspect in the description that the technological driver has on the economic growth and on the decarbonization potential. When considering such dimension, the technological driver is the only one to display, for both the utilized models, some positive economic growth effects. This quite clearly happens because the lower need for energy lowers the general production costs, hence these efficiencies improve the profitability of sectors and thus result in higher levels of GDP. The two models slightly differ in the extent of the possible rebound effects that economic growth has on the demand for energy commodities. In REMES-EU, the increase in production leads to rebound effects for energy commodities which offsets the initial decrease in demand for fossil fuels, while it leads to a large increase in demand for clean energy. In fact, according to REMES-EU, there is almost no contribution to decarbonization from this factor alone, i.e. the level of fossil fuels purchased with and without the contribution of the extra energy efficiency remains the same, but it allows decoupling the decarbonization from the growth. On the other hand, EXIOMOD does not display rebound effects on the consumption of energy commodities but agrees on the fact that the overall economic growth will improve, therefore displaying the potential that technology has on decoupling economy and climate issues.

Political Driver. The policy driver has been modeled via the inclusion of taxes growing from 0 to 5% of the price for the purchase of fossil fuels, coupled with subsidies growing from 0 to 5% of the price for the purchase of energy from clean and renewable sources. The imple-

mentation of these measures provides a significant push towards decarbonization by reducing the reliance on fossil fuels, promoting renewable energy production, and could result in a slightly negative impact on the GDP.

6. Discussion and conclusions

In this study, the macroeconomic and environmental impacts of four decarbonization scenarios have been analyzed by two different CGE models.

Our aim has been to examine the impact of various drivers and storyline features on the main economic KPIs in the decarbonization scenarios analyzed. The cap on carbon emissions is a crucial factor in the economy, as it enforces a positive carbon price and ensures that Europe shifts towards a net-zero emissions future. While all measures and behavioral changes contribute to reaching this goal, we found that technology improvement is the most effective path to reducing carbon emissions while maintaining economic growth. Policy and behavioral changes can facilitate the transition to a low-carbon system but may have slightly negative impacts on economic growth in terms of GDP. The projections by the two models show that achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 poses significant challenges, and the models struggled to find an economic equilibrium that would keep emissions below the cap, especially in the years leading up to 2050. In the case of EXIOMOD, carbon neutrality was never attainable, with a maximum reduction of 92% in emissions relative to the base year. REMES-EU managed to achieve a 95% decrease in emissions for scenario TF.

The two models could be improved in several aspects. The implementation of the labor market is relatively simple, as it assumes a fixed supply of labor, following exogenous growth trajectories. A market clearance assumption balances supply and demand of labor. Employment in man/years can be added to the analysis via the linear relationship with sectoral output. In this paper, the decision has been made not to look into employment. Under these simplifying assumptions, the figures would look very much the same as the sectoral output growth figures. The change in the labor market dynamics of a model is only worthwhile when it can be made plausible that the complex labor market system might actually significantly change the outcomes of the analysis ([28]). Existing literature shows that decarbonization policies will not have a huge impact on overall employment ([29], [7]), the impact rather takes place in specific sectors and sub-national level. Within the scope of CGE models, improvements can be made by allowing for unemployment and distinguishing between high and low-skill labor types ([29]). However, CGE models are in general constructed for the national level. CGE models with Country-level granularity will not be able to say much about sub-national distributional effects when, for example, a big metal-producing factory disappears. Different types of models (e.g. agent-based, system dynamics) need

Indicator	EXIOMOD			REMES-EU		
	Society	Technology	Policy	Society	Technology	Policy
GDP	0%	1%	0%	-3%	1%	-1%
Electricity demand	-3%	-6%	4%	-9%	-5%	4%
Fossil-based fuels	1%	-6%	-2%	-7%	0%	-2%
total value service sector	8%	1%	0%	10%	0%	0%
CO ₂ price	-6%	-1%	-2%	-7%	-3%	-3%

Table 5: Percentage change of the relevant indicator with the inclusion of the societal, technological, and policy shock (results are averaged over the relevant scenarios)

to jump in this gap when regionally asymmetric effects of the transition are concerned [30].

A relevant addition to this research could be the inclusion of the distributional effects of transition measures across income groups. Energy poverty is a widespread problem across the EU, especially with the rapidly increasing energy prices since the fall of 2021. An EU-wide survey concluded that about 8% of the population in the EU is unable to keep their houses warm during the winter months [31]. Not only are people with low incomes most likely unable to make the decision to lower their energy bill, because they lease the house they are living in. In addition, the necessary investments (solar panels, insulation, heat pumps) are also large. Thus, the energy transition measures might have as a consequence that the inequality between income groups is further increasing. To be able to analyze these effects using a CGE model, demand structures for multiple income groups with corresponding elasticities need to be included in the model.

Next, in this paper, we have taken one form of climate effects on the economy into account, namely the effect of increasing temperatures on labor productivity. Excessive heat in working environments has an effect on the efficiency of employees [32]. However, climate change effects on the economy take many more forms that could have been taken into account. The long-lasting rainfall in July 2021 that resulted in severe flooding in Western Germany and the Benelux is an example, as is the recent flooding in northern Italy. Economically, there was much damage to buildings, vehicles, livestock, and infrastructure. Indirectly, additional value-added was lost due to business processes that were disrupted. Under climate change, these floods are expected to happen more frequently [33]. The World Bank ([34]) finds that scarcity of water, another consequence of climate change, can substantially reduce GDP towards 2050, due to impacts on agriculture, health, and incomes. Moreover, the effects of wildfires on the economy are significant. It is estimated that each additional day of smoke exposure reduces local earnings by approximately 0.04% over two years [35].

The last aspect we would like to mention is the current events related to the Russian occupation of Ukraine, which also influence the energy and economic system in Europe. For this paper, we consider these events as transitory. Albeit tragic and of extreme importance for the current socioeconomic system, we assume that the time needed to re-establish a climate of international cooper-

ation similar to the previously existing one will be much shorter than the time horizon that we are considering in this paper. As the main focus of the analysis is to understand the impact that technology, society, and policy exert on the decarbonization of the EU we left out of the analysis the aforementioned aspect.

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References

- [1] S. P. Alina Bradford, What are the effects of global warming? (2022).
URL <https://www.livescience.com/37057-global-warming-effects.html>
- [2] B. Lin, Z. Jia, The energy, environmental and economic impacts of carbon tax rate and taxation industry: A cge based study in china, *Energy* 159 (2018) 558–568. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.06.167>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544218312325>
- [3] T. Zhang, Y. Ma, A. Li, Scenario analysis and assessment of china’s nuclear power policy based on the paris agreement: A dynamic cge model, *Energy* 228 (2021) 120541. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.120541>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544221007908>
- [4] K. Hainsch, K. Löffler, T. Burandt, H. Auer, P. Crespo del Granado, P. Pisciella, S. Zwickl-Bernhard, Energy transition scenarios: What policies, societal attitudes, and technology developments will realize the eu green deal?, *Energy* 239 (2022) 122067. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.122067>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S036054422102315X>
- [5] P. Crespo del Granado, H. Auer, S. Backe, P. Pisciella, K. Hainsch, Deliverable 7.1: Storylines for low carbon futures of the european energy system. (2019).
- [6] W. D. Nordhaus, *Managing the global commons: the economics of climate change*, Vol. 31, MIT press Cambridge, MA, 1994.
- [7] T. Bulavskaya, F. Reynès, Job creation and economic impact of renewable energy in the netherlands, *Renewable Energy* 119 (2018) 528–538.
- [8] R. Lewney, E. Alexandri, D. Storrie, J.-I. Antón Pérez, *Energy scenario: Employment implications of the paris climate agreement* (2019).
- [9] K. Siala, C. de la Rúa, Y. Lechón, T. Hamacher, Towards a sustainable european energy system: Linking optimization models with multi-regional input-output analysis, *Energy Strategy Reviews* 26 (2019) 100391.

- [10] Z. Vrontisi, K. Fragkiadakis, M. Kannavou, P. Capros, Energy system transition and macroeconomic impacts of a european decarbonization action towards a below 2 c climate stabilization, *Climatic Change* 162 (2020) 1857–1875.
- [11] T. Bulavskaya, J. Hu, S. Moghayer, F. Reynès, EXIOMOD 2.0: EXtended Input-Output MODel: A full description and applications, Den Haag: TNO, 2016.
- [12] L. Mathiesen, Computation of economic equilibria by a sequence of linear complementarity problems, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1985, pp. 144–162. doi:10.1007/BFb0121030.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/BFb0121030>
- [13] P. M. Pardalos, The Linear Complementarity Problem, Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 1994, pp. 39–49. doi:10.1007/978-94-015-8330-5_3.
URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-015-8330-5_3
- [14] T. F. Rutherford, Extension of gams for complementarity problems arising in applied economic analysis, *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control* 19 (8) (1995) 1299–1324. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1889\(94\)00831-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1889(94)00831-2).
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0165188994008312>
- [15] K. Stadler, R. Wood, T. Bulavskaya, C.-J. Sodersten, M. Simas, S. Schmidt, A. Usubiaga, J. Acosta-Fernández, J. Kuenen, M. Bruckner, et al., Exiobase 3, Zenodo (2019).
- [16] S. Koesler, M. Schymura, Substitution elasticities in a constant elasticity of substitution framework—empirical estimates using nonlinear least squares, *Economic Systems Research* 27 (1) (2015) 101–121.
- [17] B. D. James, D. A. DeSantis, G. Saur, Hydrogen production pathways cost analysis (2013–2016), Tech. rep., Strategic Analysis Inc., Arlington, VA (United States) (2016).
- [18] J. R. McFarland, H. J. Herzog, Incorporating carbon capture and storage technologies in integrated assessment models, *Energy Economics* 28 (5-6) (2006) 632–652.
- [19] B. C. O’Neill, M. Oppenheimer, R. Warren, S. Hallegatte, R. E. Kopp, H. O. Pörtner, R. Scholes, J. Birkmann, W. Foden, R. Licker, et al., Ipcc reasons for concern regarding climate change risks, *Nature Climate Change* 7 (1) (2017) 28–37.
- [20] E. Commission, D.-G. for Energy, Energy : roadmap 2050, Publications Office, 2012. doi:[doi/10.2833/10759](https://doi.org/10.2833/10759).
- [21] E. Commission, A clean planet for all—a european strategic long-term vision for a prosperous, modern, competitive and climate neutral economy (com (2018) 773 final) (2018).
- [22] P. Capros, A. De Vita, N. Tasios, P. Siskos, M. Kannavou, A. Petropoulos, S. Evangelopoulou, M. Zampara, D. Papadopoulos, C. Nakos, et al., Eu reference scenario 2016-energy, transport and ghg emissions trends to 2050. (2016).
- [23] OECD, Real gdp long-term forecast (indicator) (2021). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1787/d927bc18-en>.
- [24] P. Watkiss, J. Troeltzsch, K. McGlade, M. Watkiss, et al., The economic cost of climate change in europe: Synthesis report on coacch interim results. policy brief by the coacch project. (2019).
- [25] A. F. Hof, M. G. Den Elzen, D. Van Vuuren, A. Mendoza Beltran, S. Slingerland, Climate policy after kyoto. analytical insights into key issues in the climate negotiations (2011).
- [26] Climate-data, Average temperatures for countries in europe, annually (2022).
URL <https://en.climate-data.org/europe/>
- [27] A. Kelemen, W. Munch, H. Poelman, Z. Gakova, L. Dijkstra, B. Torighelli, Regions 2020, the climate change challenge for european regions. (2009).
URL https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docoffic/working/regions2020/pdf/regions2020_climat.pdf
- [28] S. Boeters, L. Savard, The labour market in cge models, ZEW-Centre for European Economic Research Discussion Paper (11-079) (2011).
- [29] J. Chateau, R. Bibas, E. Lanzi, Impacts of green growth policies on labour markets and wage income distribution: a general equilibrium application to climate and energy policies (2018).
- [30] P. García-García, Ó. Carpintero, L. Buendía, Just energy transitions to low carbon economies: A review of the concept and its effects on labour and income, *Energy Research & Social Science* 70 (2020) 101664.
- [31] E. Commission, Energy poverty (2022).
URL https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/markets-and-consumers/energy-consumer-rights/energy-poverty_en
- [32] K. Yildirim, C. Koyuncu, J. Koyuncu, et al., Does temperature affect labor productivity: Cross-country evidence, *Applied Econometrics and International Development* 9 (1) (2009) 29–39.
- [33] A. Prida, 2021 european summer floods: A warning about the climate-induced increase in flood risk? (2021).
URL <https://www.climate.axa/articles>
- [34] W. Bank, High and dry: Climate change, water, and the economy, The World Bank, 2016.
- [35] N. Reiff, How fire season affects the economy. (2022).
URL <https://www.investopedia.com/how-fire-season-affects-the-economy-5194059>

Appendix I: Main differences across the models

While both models are CGE models, some key differences explain why the two models generate different outcomes. First, they differ in the modeling structure, in the depth of data used, and in the way they model the CO₂ cap and the related price. For the purpose of this analysis, the assumptions reflecting the flexibility of the economy (e.g. elasticities) have been aligned between the two models.

Regarding the differences in the databases, even though both models consider EXIOBASE as dataset [15] the considered base years, the depth of sectors and commodities and the number of countries that are modeled explicitly are different.

Both models have the option to further aggregate regions, products, and industries. Given that the aggregation level of the base data is slightly different, the aggregation level of the modeled regions, products, and industries also differ a bit. For example, EXIOMOD has the option to consider somewhat more disaggregated electricity sectors (e.g. electricity by wind, electricity by coal, electricity by geothermal, etc.), while the database of REMES-EU only considers one electricity sector. It was chosen to keep the disaggregated electricity sectors in EXIOMOD, because it benefits the implementation of scenarios in the model.

For what concerns the modeling structure, EXIOMOD considers the equilibrium obtained by pooling the optimality conditions of the economic agents into a large-scale nonlinear system ([11]), whereas REMES-EU is modeled as a Mixed Complementarity Problem according to the Mathiesen representation for economic equilibrium problems, as shown in [12, 13, 14].

Both models use a KLEM nesting structure for the production sectors, with EXIOMOD modeling the link between the KLE and the M aggregates using a Leontief nest and defining the elasticities for the KLE nest and the KL nest according to [16], while REMES-EU defines the elasticities for each nest of the production function according to [16]. Moreover, for resource extraction sectors REMES-EU assumes a KLEM-R nesting structure, where the KLEM aggregate is further aggregated with specific capital representing the availability of the extracted resource using a small elasticity of substitution between such aggregates. A similar structure is devised for refineries to model their possibility to operate only in the presence of a mineral resource.

Next, EXIOMOD explicitly models regions representing the rest of the World. While these regions are not explicitly modeled in REMES-EU, they are exogenously given and connected to the European regions via transfers and international trade. The terms of trade ensure that, at the equilibrium, incoming and outgoing monetary flows between the EU and the rest of the World are balanced as model closure.

Households, government, and investors are modeled using a CES utility function in EXIOMOD, with an option

to shift towards a LES-CES consumption function which allows for a minimum consumption expenditure for necessary product groups. The elasticity of substitution is set to 1 - the Cobb-Douglas utility function - in REMES-EU.

Moreover, the implementation of some of the decarbonization scenarios requires a gradual uptake of hydrogen-based solutions in the economy. This translates into the inclusion of a large-scale hydrogen sector which is not operating in the base year but will play an important role towards 2050. This sector is included in a slightly different manner in each model. In EXIOMOD the two sectors (hydrogen sector and natural gas sector) are assumed to produce a very similar type of commodity, with the main difference being in the production technology. The production structure of the hydrogen sector has been defined according to data from [17]. Since there is no production of hydrogen in EXIOMOD in the base year, absolute (but neglectable) amounts of its output were added to the base year in order to construct the production structure of hydrogen in relative values to the initial output. The increasing demand for hydrogen then leads the model to gradually transition the gas sector towards the new hydrogen sector. REMES-EU considers hydrogen production to be based on three possible technologies: Electrolysis, Steam Reformation, and Steam Reformation with Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS). Each of these technologies defines a production sector that is not active in the base year, but that can become active and start producing in future time periods depending on the relative demand for such commodities and the development of prices for sectoral inputs and outputs. Each hydrogen sector is characterized by a different production technology. The development of the prices of the different input commodities will make some of the technologies more profitable than others, leading to different production mixes for hydrogen towards 2050. Also, for REMES-EU the data used to define the sectoral structures is drawn from [17], while the change in capital, labor, and electricity requirement for the production of hydrogen via Steam Reformation with CCS has been defined according to the approach in [18].

An interesting aspect of the analysis that we carry out is related to finding out the extent in which two CGE models with rather different approaches to model emissions control will yield similar results. Namely, in EXIOMOD CO₂ prices are modeled analogously to an endogenous tax on the production side, which leads to an increase in consumption prices for fossil fuels, while REMES considers CO₂ prices for emission allowances, i.e. commodities that need to be purchased alongside the fossil fuels, which leads to a decrease in demand for fossil fuels and a decrease in their price as an immediate consequence of the decrease in demand. In EXIOMOD, total emissions are estimated considering both combustion and non-combustion activities. The first ones are evaluated by multiplying the demand for fossil fuels from each sector by their CO₂ factor, while the second ones are evaluated by multiplying a suitable CO₂ coefficient by the total economic activity of the

considered sector. The total emissions need to remain below a country-specific cap defining the annual CO₂ allowed emissions. This is ensured by defining an endogenous markup (that corresponds to a shadow price of the cap) on the intermediate energy price of the given fuel. The total consumption price is given by the intermediate energy price and the markup for CO₂ prices and other taxes. The revenues stemming from emissions control are collected by the governments. In REMES-EU, the CO₂ price is defined by the environmental module in combination with the availability of CO₂ allowances. Every production sector as well as final consumers need to purchase these allowances alongside the purchase of fossil fuels. The amount of allowances needed depends on the emissions that the given fuels produce from each sector. Allowances are issued by the government of the country and purchased by the intermediate and final consumers in proportion to the purchased fuel. The price of the allowances is determined by the market according to the amount of emissions and the availability of such allowances, which is determined by the governments. Moreover, the government collects the revenue from the sale of the emission allowances.

Appendix II: Emission cap in the two models

In this Appendix, we outline the extra equations and adjustments to equations that are included to consider a carbon cap in the macroeconomic models.

EXIOMOD

The following variables are used

$CO2_r$	Exogenous cap on CO ₂ emissions.
$CO2_{r,s}^{NC}$	Non-combustion CO ₂ emissions by each industry and region
$CO2_{g,r,s}^C$	Combustion CO ₂ emissions by product emitted in each industry and region
$CO2_{g,r}^{FD}$	Combustion CO ₂ emissions by product and region emitted by final users.
$CO2REV_r$	Revenue from carbon cap.
$PCO2_r$	Price for CO ₂
$Y_{r,s}$	Output vector on industry level
$ENER_{e,r,s}$	Use of energy types
$nENER_{r,s}$	Use of aggregate energy nest
$PnENER_{r,s}$	Aggregate energy price
$PIU_{g,r,s}$	Aggregate product price for intermediate use
$PY_{r,s}$	Industry output price
$INTERUSE_{g,r,s}$	Use of intermediate inputs on aggregated product level
$CONS_{r,xx}$	Government or household (xx) consumption on aggregate product level
$CONS_{g,r,xx}$	Household or government (xx) consumption for product g
$GRINC_{r,xx}$	Gross income from households or government (xx) from production factors
$CBUD_{r,xx}$	Budget available for government or household (xx) consumption

The following parameters are used

$\alpha_{r,s}^{NC,CO_2}$	Non-combustion CO ₂ coefficient for industries
$\alpha_{e,r,xx}^{C,CO_2}$	Combustion CO ₂ coefficient for industries, households or governments (xx)
$tc_{g,r,s}$	Taxes and subsidies on products for industrial consumption
$tc_{g,r,xx}$	Tax and subsidies on products for households or governments (xx)
$eprod_{g,r,s}$	Energy productivity
$\theta_{e,r,s}^E$	Relative share parameter for types of energy within the aggregated energy nest
$\theta_{g,r,xx}^{FU}$	Relative share parameter of household (government) (xx) consumption on total household (government) demand
$\sigma_{e,r,s}^E$	Substitution of elasticity between types of energy products
$\sigma_{r,xx}^{FU}$	Substitution of elasticity between products for household or government (xx) final demand.

A cap is placed on emissions emitted in countries in

the EU. This is a country-specific cap. This cap should be equal or larger than all non-combustion ($CO2^{NC}$) and combustion ($CO2^C$) industry emissions and emissions from final use ($CO2^{FD}$).

$$\overline{CO2}_r \geq \sum_s CO2_{r,s}^{NC} + \sum_{g,s} CO2_{g,r,s}^C + \sum_g CO2_{g,r}^{FD} \quad (1)$$

The price of CO_2 ($PCO2_r$) is found via the equation of the cap and is country-specific.

Non-combustion emissions of industries are assumed to be linearly related to total economic activity ($Y_{s,r}$) of a sector (s) in a region (r) via a CO_2 -coefficient $\alpha_{r,s}^{NC,CO_2}$:

$$CO2_{r,s}^{NC} = \alpha_{r,s}^{NC,CO_2} \cdot Y_{r,s} \quad (2)$$

Combustion emissions of industries are assumed to be linearly related to non-electricity energy products (e) used by a sector in a region via CO_2 -coefficient $\alpha_{e,r,s}^{C,CO_2}$:

$$CO2_{e,r,s}^C = \alpha_{e,r,s}^{C,CO_2} \cdot ENER_{e,r,s} \quad (3)$$

Combustion emissions of final demand types households (hh) and governments (gov) are linearly related to non-electricity energy products (e) consumed by households (hh) or governments (gov) in a region via CO_2 -coefficient $\alpha_{e,r,fd}^{C,CO_2}$:

$$CO2_{e,r}^{FD} = \alpha_{e,r,hh}^{C,CO_2} \cdot CONS_{e,r,hh} + \alpha_{e,r,gov}^{C,CO_2} \cdot CONS_{e,r,gov} \quad (4)$$

Revenue from CO_2 taxation goes to the government. Where CO_2 revenue ($CO2REV$) is equal to emissions emitted in a region times the local price of CO_2 .

$$CO2REV_r = \left(\sum_s CO2_{r,s}^{NC} + \sum_{g,s} CO2_{g,r,s}^C + \sum_g CO2_{g,r}^{FD} \right) \cdot PCO2_r \quad (5)$$

Government income is equal to income from other sources like capital and labor taxes, but in the case of a carbon cap also includes income from CO_2 tax revenue.

$$GRINC_{r,gov} = income_{from\ other\ sources}_r + CO2REV_r \quad (6)$$

The CO_2 tax influences the prices for energy, which in turn influences the energy consumption decisions of industries. The price ($PnENER_{r,s}$) of aggregated energy nest ($nENER$) is a weighted average of the intermediate energy price adjusted for industry taxes and CO_2 tax.

$$PnENER_{r,s} \cdot nENER_{r,s} = \sum_e PIU_{e,r,s} \cdot ENER_{e,r,s} \cdot \left(1 + tc_{e,r,s} + PCO2_r \cdot \alpha_{e,r,s}^{C,CO_2} \right) \quad (7)$$

The demand for individual energy products in the energy nest is also responding to the additional CO_2 price on non-electricity energy products

$$ENER_{r,s} = \left(\frac{nENER_{r,s}}{eprod_{e,r,s}} \right) \cdot \theta_{e,r,s}^E \cdot \left(\frac{PIU_{e,r,s} \left(1 + tc_{e,r,s} + PCO2_r \cdot \alpha_{e,r,s}^{C,CO_2} \right)}{eprod_{e,r,s} PnENER_{r,s}} \right)^{-\sigma_{r,s}^E} \quad (8)$$

The CO_2 taxes are included as an extra cost for industries.

Industrial output price is directly affected by taxation of emissions. Industry price (PY) is found via the zero-profit condition. Revenues earned from product sales less possible production net taxes are equal to the cost of intermediate inputs and factors of production. In the case of the carbon cap, there are additional taxes that need to be paid for the emissions.

$$Y_{r,s} \cdot PY_{r,s} = \sum_g (INTERUSE_{g,r,s} \cdot PIU_{g,r,s} \cdot (1 + tc_{g,r,s})) + \left(CO2_{r,s}^{NC} + \sum_g CO2_{g,r,s}^C \right) \cdot PCO2_r + othertaxes_{g,r,s} + production_factors \quad (9)$$

The budgets of households ($CBUD_H$) and governments ($CBUD_G$) are also affected by the carbon cap. The following equations for not define household and government budget, however, define the scaling parameter of the household and government consumption ($SCLFD_H$ and $SCLFD_G$). Consumption prices of households and governments are given by PC_H and PC_G . Taxation of consumption is given by t_ch

$$CBUD_H_r = \sum_g (CONS_H_r \cdot PC_H_{g,r} \cdot \left(1 + tc_{g,r,hh} + PCO2_r \cdot \alpha_{g,r,hh}^{C,CO_2} \right)) \quad (10)$$

$$CBUD_G_r = \sum_g (CONS_G_r \cdot PC_G_{g,r} \cdot \left(1 + tc_{g,r,gov} + PCO2_r \cdot \alpha_{g,r,gov}^{C,CO_2} \right)) \quad (11)$$

Household and government consumption looks as follows under a carbon cap:

$$CONS_H_{g,r} = CBUD_H_r \cdot \theta_{g,r,hh}^{FU} \cdot \left(1 + tc_{g,r,hh} + PCO2_r \cdot \alpha_{g,r,hh}^{C,CO_2} \right)^{\sigma_{r,hh}^{FU}} \quad (12)$$

$$CONS_G_{g,r} = CBUD_G_r \cdot \theta_{g,r,gov}^{FU} \cdot \left(1 + tc_{g,r,gov} + PCO2_r \cdot \alpha_{g,r,gov}^{C,CO_2} \right)^{\sigma_{r,gov}^{FU}} \quad (13)$$

REMES-EU

REMES-EU is modeled after the Mathiesen format for CGE models. This format considers the CGE as a Mixed Complementarity Problem consisting of three conditions. A zero-profit condition defining whether a sector is in activity or not, a market-clearing condition requiring the supply to match the demand for all commodities through the definition of a price, and finally an income balance constraint, requiring all the expenditure by consumers to match their income after taxes are paid and savings are set apart. To describe how CO₂ allowances are modeled in REMES-EU let us introduce the following notation:

Cost shares

$\theta_{r,s,g}^{OUT}$	Benchmark share of output of commodity g produced by sector s in country r
$\theta_{r,s}^M$	Benchmark share of materials in the aggregate output of sector s in country r
$\theta_{r,s}^E$	Benchmark share of energy in the aggregate output of sector s in country r
$\theta_{r,s}^K$	Benchmark share of capital in the value-added aggregate of sector s in country r
$\theta_{r,s}^L$	Benchmark share of capital in the value-added aggregate of sector s in country r
$\theta_{r,s,g}$	Benchmark share of commodity g in its aggregate in sector s and country r
$\theta_{r,s,ET}$	Benchmark share of electricity generation and transmission in sector s and country r
$\beta_{r,h,g}$	Benchmark share of consumption of commodity g by consumer group h in country r

Elasticities

$\sigma_{r,s}^{KL}$	Elasticity of substitution between capital and labor in sector s and region r
$\sigma_{r,s}^{KLE}$	Elasticity of substitution between energy and capital-labor aggregate in sector s and region r
$\sigma_{r,s}^{KLEM}$	Elasticity of substitution between materials and capital-labor-energy aggregate in sector s and region r
$\sigma_{r,s}^E$	Elasticity of substitution between energy inputs in the energy composite in sector s and region r

Other parameters

$\alpha_{s,g}^{CO_2}$	CO ₂ emission coefficient for energy good g in sector s
$\alpha_{h,g}^{CO_2}$	CO ₂ emission coefficient for energy good g for consumer h
$tc_{r,g}$	Consumption tax rate for good g in region r
$tp_{r,s}$	Production tax rate for output of sector s in region r
$\gamma_{r,s}^L$	Productivity of labor in sector s and region r
$CO_{2,r}$	CO ₂ cap in country r

Price variables

$pa_{r,g}$	Consumption price of commodity g in region r
$pr_{r,s,g}$	Output price of commodity g from sector s in region r
$rkcr$	Return to capital in region r
pl_r	Wage rate in region r
$p_r^{CO_2}$	Price of emission allowances in region r
$pu_{r,h}$	Consumption price index for consumer group or institution h

Activity variables

$Y_{r,s}$	Activity level of sector s in region r
$U_{r,h}$	Welfare for consumer h region r

The zero-profit condition is defined using the unit revenue and the unit cost for each sector. For a typical sector s in country r the unit profit is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{r,s} = & \sum_g \theta_{r,s,g}^{OUT} \left[\frac{pr_{r,s,g}}{\bar{p}_{r,s,g}} (1 - tp_{r,s}) \right] - \\ & \left\{ \sigma_{r,s}^M \left[\sum_{g \in M} \theta_{r,s,g} \frac{pa_{r,g}}{\bar{p}_{r,g}} (1 - tc_{r,g}) \right]^{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^{KLEM}} \right. \\ & + (1 - \sigma_{r,s}^M) \left[(1 - \sigma_{r,s}^E) \left(\theta_{r,s}^K rkcr^{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^{KL}} + \theta_{r,s}^L \gamma_{r,s}^L pl^{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^{KL}} \right)^{\frac{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^{KLE}}{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^{KLE}}} \right. \\ & + \theta_{r,s}^E \left(\sum_{g \in FE} \theta_{r,s,g} \left(\frac{pa_{r,g}}{\bar{p}_{r,g}} (1 + tc_{r,g}) + \alpha_{s,g}^{CO_2} \cdot p_r^{CO_2} \right)^{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^E} \right. \\ & + \sum_{g \in CE \setminus ET} \theta_{r,s,g} \left(\frac{pa_{r,g}}{\bar{p}_{r,g}} (1 - tc_{r,g})^{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^E} \right) + \\ & \left. \left. \theta_{r,s,ET} \left(\theta_{r,s,ele} \frac{pa_{r,ele}}{\bar{p}_{r,ele}} (1 + tc_{r,ele}) + \right. \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \left. \theta_{r,s,etr} \frac{pa_{r,etr}}{\bar{p}_{r,etr}} (1 + tc_{r,etr}) \right)^{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^E} \right]^{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^{KLEM}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{1 - \sigma_{r,s}^{KLEM}}} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

We can see that the commodities related to fossil energy sources (FE) are aggregated with the purchase of CO₂ allowances at price $p_r^{CO_2}$ according to a proportional factor $\alpha_{s,g}^{CO_2}$ according to a Leontief technology. Such conditions are paired with the activity level of the sector so that when the zero-profit condition is satisfied the sector will operate with a non-negative activity level, i.e.

$$0 \leq \Pi_{r,s} \perp Y_{r,s} \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

Analogously, households consider the following expendi-

ture function.

$$\begin{aligned}
e_{r,h} &= \prod_{g \in G \setminus E} \left(\frac{pa_{r,g}}{\bar{p}a_{r,g}} (1 + tc_{r,g}) \right)^{\beta_{r,h,g}} \cdot \\
&\cdot \prod_{g \in FE} \left(\frac{pa_{r,g}}{\bar{p}a_{r,g}} (1 + tc_{r,g}) + \alpha_{h,g}^{CO_2} p_r^{CO_2} \right)^{\beta_{r,h,g}} \cdot \\
&\prod_{g \in CE \setminus ET} \left(\frac{pa_{r,g}}{\bar{p}a_{r,g}} (1 + tc_{r,g}) \right)^{\beta_{r,h,g}} \cdot \\
&\cdot \left(\theta_{r,h,ele} \frac{pa_{r,ele}}{\bar{p}a_{r,ele}} (1 + tc_{r,ele}) + \theta_{r,h,etr} \frac{pa_{r,etr}}{\bar{p}a_{r,etr}} (1 + tc_{r,etr}) \right)^{\beta_{r,h,ET}}
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

The expenditure function for each consumption source (households, government, and investors) is paired with the welfare level of the consumer to satisfy the condition

$$pu_{r,h} \leq e_{r,s} \perp U_{r,h} \geq 0 \tag{17}$$

According to Hotellings' Lemma, differentiating the unit profit function with respect to input and output prices provides compensated demand and supply coefficients. In particular, the demand for CO₂ allowances from the different sectors is defined as

$$\sum_s \frac{\partial \Pi_{r,s}}{\partial p_r^{CO_2}} Y_{r,s}$$

while for consumers and institutions, such demand is computed as

$$\sum_h \frac{\partial e_{r,h}}{\partial p_r^{CO_2}} U_{r,h}$$

The market clearing condition for CO₂ emission allowances in Country r is defined as

$$0 \leq p_r^{CO_2} \perp \bar{CO}_{2,r} - \sum_s \frac{\partial \Pi_{r,s}}{\partial p_r^{CO_2}} Y_{r,s} + \sum_h \frac{\partial e_{r,h}}{\partial p_r^{CO_2}} U_{r,h} \geq 0 \tag{18}$$

where $e_{r,h}$ denotes the expenditure function of the h final consumer (households, government, and investors) and $\bar{CO}_{2,r}$ is the CO₂ cap.